

AN OVERVIEW OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN AGRICULTURE IN TURKİYE AND CHALLENGES FACED

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ABSTRACT

Digital transformation in agriculture is applied in many areas, such as irrigation, fertilization, and pest management, contributing both to increasing productivity and to the sustainable use of resources. This study examines the development and current state of digital transformation in agriculture in Türkiye. Focus group meetings were conducted to identify the challenges encountered by stakeholders, which were classified and prioritized under three categories: technical/technological, governance/legislation/policy, and socio-economic barriers. The results revealed that the primary barriers are the lack of inter-institutional data sharing, the inadequacy of existing legislation and policies in supporting digital transformation, and insufficient budgets allocated for R&D activities. Proposed solutions to address these priority barriers include the establishment of a common platform for data sharing, development of incentive mechanisms for small-scale enterprises, and promotion of farmers' active involvement in R&D processes. The findings demonstrate that digital transformation process should be evaluated holistically, encompassing not only technical but also social and economic dimensions.

Keywords: Agriculture, Digital Transformation, Automation, Focus Group